

DESIGN METHODS AS AN OPPORTUNITY TO DIAGNOSIS THE PROCESS OF A CHILD'S ADAPTATION TO SCHOOL AND ELIMINATE EXISTING DIFFICULTIES

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Abstract. This article describes the possibilities of diagnosing the successful transition of children to school, preventing social difficulties and psychocorrection using projection techniques. Also, the diagnosis is characterized by the fact that strategies are presented that allow the child to overcome the consequences of school stress.

Key words: adaptation to school, projective diagnostics, stress, effective strategy, projection methods, meditation, imaginary journey.

МЕТОДЫ ДИЗАЙНА КАК ВОЗМОЖНОСТЬ ДИАГНОСТИКИ ПРОЦЕССА АДАПТАЦИИ РЕБЕНКА К ШКОЛЕ И УСТРАНЕНИЯ СУЩЕСТВУЮЩИХ ТРУДНОСТЕЙ

Аннотация. В статье описаны возможности диагностики успешного перехода детей в школу, профилактики социальных трудностей и психокоррекции с использованием проекционных методик. Также диагноз характеризуется тем, что представлены стратегии, позволяющие ребенку преодолеть последствия школьного стресса.

Ключевые слова: адаптация к школе, проективная диагностика, стресс, эффективная стратегия, методы проецирования, медитация, воображаемое путешествие.

Many children of preschool and primary school age experience significant difficulties adapting to school. They have a number of problems that they cannot solve: inability to adapt to school demands, anatomical and physiological fatigue, as a result of which they face emotional stress. Early diagnosis, prevention and correction of difficulties at school is always a pressing and extremely important problem in preventing such problems. In this case, it is necessary not only to identify adaptation difficulties, but also to carry out practical work that makes it possible to develop an effective strategy for overcoming existing stress in order to overcome the difficulties of adaptation to school. Early identification of difficulties in the process of children's adaptation to school requires great responsibility from the practical school psychologist.

Many children find it difficult to adapt to school. Children face a number of problems that they cannot solve on their own. Therefore, early diagnosis, prevention and correction of difficulties in adapting to school is always a pressing and extremely important problem.

For example, to prevent existing difficulties, it is advisable to use effective psychodiagnostic methods for diagnosing the successful transition of children to school. In this case, the use of projective methods that are convenient for practical psychologists and students is essential. The use of projective methods, which is a method of art therapy, allows, firstly, to increase students' interest in the process, and secondly, to determine in detail their mental state.

Also, in addition to diagnostic information, these are simultaneously strategies that allow the child to cope with the consequences of adaptive stress (see coping, coping strategy) - actions taken by a person to overcome stress, that is, to overcome psychologically. In difficult situations, the experience of emotional reactions that combine those used cognitive, emotional and behavioral strategies (in the sense of eliminating the negative consequences of stress), also plays the role of a coping strategy.

The technique combines the features of the cathartic projection technique (which allows you to effectively respond to internal experiences) and the analysis of creative products (drawing).

Projective methods are test materials specially organized and used to study a person or his individual aspects. The effect of these methods is based on the projection mechanism. This mechanism was first discovered by S. Freud and described as a process of combining feelings and desires that are unacceptable to a person with an external object. Projection is unconscious in nature and performs a protective function, mitigating conflicts between a person's real (unconscious) aspirations and social norms, values and conscious beliefs. The term "projective" itself was introduced in 1939 by L. Frank (L. K. Frank, American psychologist) to designate a number of methods known by that time. He also managed to create a classification of them according to selected characteristics, which, with some additions, is still used in our time.

In psychology, especially in kindergarten, more attention is paid to projection methods. Projective methods are the simplest way of expressing a child's attitude to the environment, to himself, to what is happening, that is, based on the age characteristics of these children, they are aimed at identifying as fully as possible everything that cannot be determined by observation. or conversation. Drawing is a teaching method that does not require stress, but on the contrary, gives children pleasure and joy. It's hard to find a child who doesn't like to draw and play. Thus, the child's attention is correctly directed to specific activities. The technique combines the properties of cathartic projection and provides significant support for the projection of the internal psychological state.

Projective psychodiagnostics also has an aspect characteristic of play: it would be an exaggeration to say that the child feels as if immersed in the activity of the game, in the course of a fairy tale, which gives him great pleasure and thereby creates and maintains the necessary motivation. However, along with the advantages of projection methods, there are also disadvantages. Firstly, there is a problem of standardization of this type of research, in which the quality and content of the interpretation largely depends on the professionalism of the diagnostician and the concept of its interpretation. In this regard, the reliability of the data obtained may be questioned.

Projective methods are qualitative rather than quantitative; they may indicate deviation from the norm, but almost never tell us anything specific about the indicators of this deviation. Therefore, to increase the reliability of diagnostic results, it is necessary to combine the method with other tests that provide more accurate and rigorous data. However, it should be remembered that serious diagnostic conclusions cannot be drawn on the basis of any one projection method. Its results should always be double-checked with the help of other independent sources of information: more formalized tests, pedagogical observation data, diagnostic interviews, biographical data, and parent surveys are acceptable.

Of great importance in working with children with different emotional characteristics are methods of image projection, which create great opportunities for diagnosing shyness, silence, modesty, aggressiveness, stubbornness, willfulness and other characteristics. Projections also allow you to establish contact with the child and psychologists.

The projective method “Tree in a Thunderstorm” we propose covers both diagnostic and psychotherapeutic functions and is aimed at combining diagnostic techniques and meditative exercises. At the same time, in addition to diagnostic information, it is possible to teach self-management strategies that allow the child to overcome the consequences of stress that arises when adapting to school demands.

This “Tree in a Thunderstorm” method is the result of a cross-adaptation of the integral game exercise “Tree” by the German positivist psychologist Klaus Foppel and the Phillips school adaptation test. This complex exercise is used in working with first-graders as a correction for their mental development and emerging difficulties. When working with children of preschool and primary school age, practical psychologists will have sufficient diagnostic information to find a solution to the problem if, using the “Tree in a Thunderstorm” projection diagnostic technique, they can determine whether they will successfully go through periods of adaptation to a new educational institution.

Also, all signs of the material obtained from the analysis of the “Tree in a Thunderstorm” method are interpreted in a symbolic sense. Projection methods do not accurately describe a specific human function, so it is not practical to name them separately, since they are limited to the study of the motivational or, for example, intellectual sphere, like tests. Because the results are obtained using projective methods are aimed at a comprehensive study of personality. That is why today most psychologists prefer to use this method.

Therefore, the projective method “Tree in a Thunderstorm” is also used as a drawing method in working with children of preschool and primary school age; it is convenient and safe to use in groups and individually. The tasks in these test instructions are easy for children to complete, that is, they are understood without difficulty, do not require a high level of speech development, and at the same time, the pictures make it easy to start a conversation and attract the attention of children. child. As we noted above, the “Tree in a Thunderstorm” projection technique is an example of diagnosing the process of children’s adaptation to school and combining meditative exercises into it. In addition to diagnostic information, it simultaneously allows the child to overcome the negative consequences of adaptive stress and teach self-management strategies.

The technique combines the features of the cathartic projection technique, that is, it helps to overcome internal anxiety and fear, transfers the tension that arises during the drawing process to external objects, and serves to analyze the level of the child’s creative abilities.

Initially, the meditation process is carried out on children. At the same time, the researcher slowly and calmly says the following text: “Stand next to the chair, remaining relaxed and keeping your body in a relaxed position. Take a deep breath and close your eyes. Feel your feet, how firmly they stand on the floor. Imagine, you have new roots growing that branch into the ground. Some of them are thick and strong, covering the entire area around you. Imagine that these roots are holding your body firmly to the ground. you can spread your arms and imagine that the branches are fed by sunlight, and a light breeze supports your body, and no storm will harm you... The wind

begins to blow stronger and stronger, the storm shakes. trees. Your trunk may bend from side to side, and some branches may break, but you are so strong on the ground that the storm cannot knock you down... Feel your roots, body and branches, feel how strong and flexible you are. Let the wind blow, your branches will bend under its force, but will not break... Gradually the wind subsides. The sun comes out from behind the clouds and you enjoy the peace around you... you become yourself again. Stretch, relax, take a deep breath and open your eyes...

Children draw what they imagined after the “imaginary journey”. The pictures are discussed individually with each child in a narrative form.

Materials: colored pencils, sheets of white paper in A-4 format for children. Pri obrabotke i interpretatsii resultatsiya uchytyvaetsya informatsiya, sootvetstvuyushchaya vsem grapho-proektsionnym methods diagnostics, namely:

- prostranstvennoe sostoyanie;
- Size image;
- characteristic line;
- sila najatiya pera;
- context imagery.

Children's drawing can be analyzed, conditionally divided into 3 groups:

The first group is a tree, a picture and a terrible time. Rebenok ispytyvaet stress. On chuvstvuet slojnye i nekomfortnye situatsii, to est osnovnye emotsii kotorye on ispytyvaet, otritsatelnye.

The second group - drawing an image of a thunderstorm is an indication that the consequences of the thunderstorm are still present in the pictures, but the sun is shining, the rains have stopped, the child feels relief and his emotions are stabilizing.

The third group - eto izobrajenie kokonchaniya grozy, to est snova zasiyaet solntse. Neither photography is more nor vidny posledstviya hurricane. And in some cases, increased comfort characterizes the child's adaptation to the school environment, his self-confidence, and his typical persistence.

In conclusion, it will be said that the systematic organization of preschool education will increase the child's correct schooling, and this process will increase the possibility of mutual harmony between learning and school life. In connection with satiim, various training sessions conducted by preschoolers and teachers create consistency in the formation of ix basic competencies. It is the use of projective techniques that influences the mental activity of schoolchildren and the formation of their attitude towards the environment.

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